

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 680395.

Reactor Optimization by Membrane Enhanced Operation

H2020-SPIRE-2015 - RIA n° 680395

Start Date: 14th **September 2015**

Project Coordinator: Prof. Robert Franke – Evonik - DE

Email: robert.franke@evonik.com

Deliverable
Report
External Advisory Board
D8.5_WP8_EMH
Public

Author(s): G.M.RIOS (EMH)

Task No. : 8.3

Deliverable No. : 8.5

Issue Date: 10.07.2016

Number of pages:

Identifier: D8.5_WP8_EMH

Summary:

An **External Advisory Board** is set up for the ROMEO project. The report briefly recalls its **objectives / missions** and gives its **composition**.

Document history and validation

When	Who	Type	Comments
04.07.2016	G.M.RIOS (EMH)	Preparation version 1 (V1)	

Author(s):	G.M.RIOS (EMH)	Approved by the Coordinator : Yes, Kristen Date: 01-08.2016
Reviewer(s) :	E.KASSADJIAN (EMH)	

Content

1. Objectives & missions.....	4
2. Composition.....	4
3. How it will work?	4

1. Objectives & missions

It has been proposed that an External Advisory Board (EAB) accompany the ROMEO project from the start to the end.

Composed of a few experts not directly involved in the project, representing institutions able to advise on important points related to societal/economic issues of the project, the EAB will conduct a critical review of the project progress.

It will also make recommendations on priorities aimed to reach more easily project objectives and to increase their impacts; notably concerning new routes for important reactions such as hydroformylation, low temperature water gas shift or new very advanced concepts such as SILP (Supported Ionic Liquid Phase), SILM (Supported Ionic Liquid Membrane) and flexible tool-box involving different “building blocks”.

Three meetings have been programmed at months 18, 30 and 42.

2. Composition

After discussions about experts able to carry out these tasks, while being accepted by all members of the consortium (regarding notably privacy or potential conflict of interest criteria), the next choice was done:

- 1) Dr. Andreas Geisbauer
Clariant Produkte (Deutschland) GmbH
Waldheimer Str. 13 - 83052 Bruckmühl, Germany
Andreas.Geisbauer@clariant.com

- 2) Prof. dr. Freek Kapteijn
Catalysis Engineering-ChemE - TU Delft
Julianalaan 136 – 2628 BL Delft, The Netherlands
F.Kapteijn@tudelft.nl

- 3) Mr. Herman Bottenberg
Zeton B.V
Marssteden 206 - 7547 TD Enschede, The Netherlands
Herman.Bottenberg@zeton.nl

3. How it will work?

A non-disclosure agreement will be put in place before details can be shared with the EAB members. Evonik will be in charge of preparing the document.

During the 2nd progress meeting to be held in Copenhagen in September 2016, it should be made clear within the ROMEO steering committee meeting, which information the EAB members should get.

Another point will be checked to make this information available to the EAB members in a secure way: having a dedicated area in our existing “team room¹” or opening a second secured space dedicated to the EAB members only.

The first meeting of the EAB should be held in Brussels in March/April 2017.

¹ The Team Room is a secured website hosted by Evonik and only available to the ROMEO members.